

Dynamic antenna azimuth planning for 3G, 4G and future 5G broadband radio networks

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Abstract—The increasing volume of wireless traffic expected by mobile networks worldwide, means that the wireless industry is searching ways on how to serve the mobile users more efficiently and cost effectively. The mobile users served by any wireless network need to have at least the required radio coverage to enable the demanded wireless network connectivity while on top the offered network capacity needs to provide the maximum coverage footprint with maximum application throughput. Managing the available capacity in a mobile network is becoming an important technical and financial issue for all mobile operators' daily operational activities. Any wireless user served, requires high signal to noise and interference ratio (SINR) in order to get optimum service. When SINR is at its best, the radio access network (RAN) offers more revenue and satisfied customers for the mobile operators. In this paper, we focus on how to optimise a mobile network service performance by fine tuning the antenna azimuth headings, such that the geographical coverage area (GEO) of the antenna can serve more users with better radio conditions. Through dynamic antenna azimuth planning, a constant average SINR gain can be achieved. This average SINR gain improves the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) of the network. In principle, a remote azimuth steering system and method is proposed and applied in a real basestation site as a solution to improve the network performance in a self organizing (SON) manner.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's mobile networks, improving quality of service (QoS) for mobile users is of global interest to both industry and academia. In this paper, we aim at enhancing QoS of the mobile users served by steering the antenna azimuth heading to the "majority" of users distributed clockwise or counterclockwise towards the cell edge in the horizontal plane. One possible solution is to deploy a dynamic and reconfigurable network which can adapt to the dynamic nature of the distribution of mobile users [1], [2]. Other possible solutions such as deployed device-to-device communication around cell edge of the macro cell, coordinated multipoint (CoMP) MIMO techniques, 3D beamforming and antenna azimuth beam switching have been suggested in the cell edge coverage and throughput improvement [3]–[6]. Specific to this paper is the use of the automatic antenna azimuth steering techniques which can adjust the antenna azimuth headings in real time. Unlike the traditional antenna azimuth beam steering which is based on a beamforming network requires antenna system swap and new (e)NodeB features, the dynamic antenna azimuth control system described herein is attached

to any basestation platform and used for any existing or future antenna system available in the market. To verify our method, KPI's such as Access Failure Rate (AFR), Drop Call Rate (DCR), Voice Traffic (Erlang) and Data Traffic (MB) in a live mobile network are measured and compared.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The dynamic antenna azimuth need is described in Section II. The theoretical benefits of dynamic antenna azimuth planning in a mobile network is explained in Section III. Trial measurements statistics from live mobile networks are demonstrated and discussed in Section IV. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. THE NEED OF DYNAMIC AZIMUTH PLANNING

Today, in the first phase of base station deployment, mobile network operators use radio network planning tools to provide the coverage for the geographical area that a base station (or cells) needs to cover. To achieve this purpose, they simulate coverage (i.e E_c) and interference (i.e I_o) taking into account the transmitter (T_x) and receiver (R_x) parameters of both the Base Station (BS) and Mobile Station (MS) in the coverage area, forming typical link-budgets. The main problem this technique faces is the fact that it does not take into account the performance aspects of the BS-MS radio links (i.e planning for the E_b or for the traffic portion of power amplifiers). It is obvious that enabling radio planning by simulating for the generated future traffic is a very complicated task (if not impossible) with the available systems and tools a mobile network operator has in hand. Actual network usage in the service area, RNC system decision processes in real time as well as usage-traffic prediction models in time and location are some of the missing information to provide the optimum radio plan needed to account for the performance of a new base station. To tackle the problem we know that a dynamic radio planning technique needs to be enforced. The term dynamic herein refers to the fact that since usage and traffic in a cell's GEO area is dynamic, network coverage should also be dynamic. The RNC is trying to enable this dynamic radio planning by utilizing the well known power control features. We know that these features are aiming to enhance the BS-MS radio link performance under various interference, load and radio propagation conditions. However, this is not enough or optimum. Turning to the base station

antenna, we see that the remote electrical tilt (RET) is the only available possible antenna feature to help the mobile network planning needs. Today, with the aid of a sophisticated self organizing network platform (SON), the electrical tilt may be used to tackle the interference at the cell edge and boost the radio links near the base station. Of course at the expense of cell radius which sooner or later requires additional base station investments in the cluster or service area of the cells. Figure 1 shows a simulated 12-element antenna azimuth radiation pattern with 60° beamwidth and 18.3dBi gain which is matched for industrial purposes. The mobile traffic randomly distributed in it is represented by dots here. Since the load distribution is highly inhomogeneous in the GEO coverage area of cell, the signal quality per user in time is expected to be inhomogeneous nature as well.

Fig. 1. 12-element Antenna azimuth Radiation Pattern.

Figure 2 shows two snapshots of load distribution in a 120° typical hexagonal cell where in this example most of mobile users are located outside the antenna's main beam. In order to provide enhanced performance for the mobile users across the cell, it is necessary to track the cell-edge high usage areas clockwise or counterclockwise the antenna main beam. Here, we propose a dynamic antenna azimuth fine tuning and control system which can automatically adjust the antenna's azimuth headings to follow such high usage areas in time and space. By exchanging in the link budgets the antenna gain with the amplifier RF power resources (through the systems embedded power control mechanism), the overall cell performance in a power limited radio access network (RAN) can be enhanced.

III. THEORETICAL APPROACH

In order to verify this concept, the antenna parameter chosen here to enhance the cell's KPIs in the mobile network is azimuth. The antenna azimuth is the direction defined through the radio planning process referenced to the true north, to which the antenna needs to be pointed. Figure 3 illustrates a base transceiver station (BTS) located in a 3-sector cellular network. Consider in a Single-input Single-output (SISO)

Fig. 2. Two snapshots of uneven distribution of loads in a cell.

system, a user m located towards the edge of the cell, in the observation area which is denoted as position (x,y) . The received power, in dBm at user m from the cell n is given by the equation(1) below.

$$P_{n,m} = 10 \log_{10}(P) + G(\theta_{n,m}, \varphi_{n,m}) - L_{n,m} + G_m \quad (1)$$

Where P is the antenna transmitted power in the traffic channel, $L_{n,m}$ is the free space path loss between the user m and cell n and G_m is the gain of the receive antenna and assumed to be isotropic. $G(\theta_{n,m}, \varphi_{n,m})$ is the gain of the basestation antenna for a given elevation $\theta_{n,m}$ and azimuth $\varphi_{n,m}$ between the basestation n and user m . Referring to Figure 3, the angle $\Phi_{n,m}$ between the line-of-sight and the true north is dependent on the location of the user in the x - y coordinates and it can be calculated in the horizontal plane as the following:

$$\phi_{n,m} = \arctan\left(\frac{\Delta y(n,m)}{\Delta x(n,m)}\right) \quad (2)$$

The path loss used here can be assumed as free space path loss model for simplicity and is shown as:

$$L_{n,m} = \left(\frac{4\pi d_{n,m} f}{c}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Where f is the transmission frequency of the antenna (Hz), $d_{n,m}$ is the distance between the n^{th} basestation and the user m . The angle $\varphi_{n,m}$ between the line-of-sight and the center of antenna's main lobe, in the horizontal plane, can be expressed as following:

$$\varphi_{n,m} = \Phi_{n,m} + \Phi_n \quad (4)$$

Where Φ_n is the antenna azimuth angle in radians. Assuming the received power from the remaining sectors is treated as interference, $I_{n,m}$. The signal to noise plus interference ratio and Shannon capacity for the user m and for the simple SISO scenario examined herein is therefore given by (5) and (6)

$$SINR_m = \frac{P_{n,m}}{I_{n,m} + P_n} \quad (5)$$

$$C_m = B \log_2(1 + SINR_m) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 3. A layout showing antenna parameters in the horizontal plane.

Where B is the bandwidth of the signal and P_n is the thermal noise at the receiver. The influence of the antenna azimuth steering on the cell capacity can be captured from equations derived here. Considering a fixed Half-power beamwidth (HPBW) angle, and depending on the location of a certain user m , as the angle $\varphi_{n,m}$ decreases, the SINR for the user m increases based on equation 5. Knowing that power control mechanisms exist in any power limited RAN technology, in order for the RNC to satisfy the Block Error Rate (BLER) targets of any active mobile user in the cell, we expect that the antenna gain boosts in the link-budgets for the majority of our users will be exchanged proportionally with direct power gain in the respective traffic channel power availability. This saved power resources will be ultimately used by the RNC to the active mobile users in need as the power amplifier transmits the maximum available at all times.

The motivation in this paper is to prove that an antenna azimuth fine tuning technique that aims at dynamically tracking the high usage areas in the antenna horizontal radiation space can optimize the power link budgets which in turn can be used by the RNC to enhance SINR for all users served.

IV. AUTOMATIC ANTENNA AZIMUTH PLANNING

In this section, an automatic antenna azimuth planning is presented which can steer basestation antenna's azimuth automatically by a control unit through remote management software based on the Antenna Interface Standards Group (AISG) protocols [7]. Different from other antenna azimuth steering techniques, this automatic antenna azimuth mounting can keep intact the gain of the antenna while offering flexibility in the needed steering range. The automatic antenna azimuth mounting is comprised of a robotic control unit and a antenna frame respectively. The robotic control unit is comprised of a stepper motor engine, directionality sensors and sophisticated electronics that can automatically steer the basestation antenna to the desired direction. The basestation antenna is attached to the antenna frame which is connected

with the robotic control unit beneath it. The automatic antenna azimuth mounting designed here can be installed in any legacy or future basestation platform. Figure 4 shows the antenna azimuth mounting installed in a real basestation platform with Commscope antenna and Nokia (e)NodeB.

Fig. 4. Antenna azimuth steering mountings in real basestation platform.

V. TEST IN LIVE MOBILE NETWORKS

In this section, the proposed automatic antenna azimuth implementation strategy in live mobile networks is demonstrated in this section. The first step in the strategy is to identify a cell/cluster in live mobile networks which can be optimised. Usually, selected KPIs within this cell/cluster are below network average. After that, the cell/site in the cluster needs to be selected for dynamic antenna azimuth steering implementation. The selection criteria of the cell/site is based on the conditions of high traffic load, large inter-site distance (ISD) (greater than 750m is optimal for our applications). In order to define the high usage areas in the chosen cell, the automatic antenna azimuth scanning feature is operated for a predefined time scale. In order to effectively optimise the network performance without jeopardizing the original coverage of the cell/site, the antenna azimuth steering range is chosen for the 60° HPBW antenna of our test from -15° to $+15^\circ$ (30° scanning range) per 15° step in the horizontal plane. Through scanning the 3 discrete azimuth headings ($-15^\circ, 0^\circ, +15^\circ$) in the selected cell/site for 15 minutes each during the course of a day week for a predefined time scale, the traffic load in these 3 azimuth headings is recorded in the Operating Support System (OSS). By counting and analyzing the traffic load in these 3 azimuth headings, the high usage area in the cell/site can be decided per discrete time period via using the recorded OSS statistics among the 3 azimuth headings. The

Fig. 5. Coverage area for the cell of Aspropirgos.

new neighbor relationships in this cluster need to be set as well. By using the optimized azimuth heading in the cell/site for the predefined time scales, the KPIs per cell/cluster from the OSS of the basestation can be collected and evaluated. By comparing the KPIs for each azimuth heading, we can evaluate the optimum antenna directions in time for this cell/cluster. Details of the technique followed for the dynamic azimuth decision algorithm can be found in [8]

Real network performance results are carried out in a mobile network in Athens, Greece. The trial area selected here is Thriasio Pedio. The number of cells in this area implemented the antenna azimuth steering units is 35 and the total number of cells in this area is over 100. One of the selected cells used to perform this trial test is called Aspropirgos which is a seafront area located in the northwest outside of Athens. Based on the cell/site selection criteria, the cell Aspropirgos_L(272) is chosen to implement the dynamic antenna azimuth planning feature proposed. The coverage area of cell Aspropirgos is shown in Figure 5 and the cell Aspropirgos_L(272) is indicated by a yellow circle in it.

A. Confirmation of Coverage-Drive testing

In order to verify the GEO coverage of the selected cell will not change before and after implementing the antenna azimuth steering in the chosen cell Aspropirgos_L(272), NEMO Outdoor drive testing was used to compare the GEO coverage variation. In this driving test, the UE device was locked to the cell Aspropirgos_L(272) before and after the antenna azimuth implementation in it. Referring to Figure 6, it can be seen that the GEO coverage of the chosen cell before and after the antenna azimuth offset to 15° is the same, as all the samples of Received Signal Code Power (RSCP) for the UE during these two tests are above -105dBm the minimum coverage threshold that allows connectivity in a broadband mobile network.

B. Dynamic Antenna Azimuth Steering

The paper now considers the user traffic variation pattern appearing in a day course is repeatable. The typical data traffic

Fig. 6. Real GEO coverage of cell Aspropirgos (a) before (b) after antenna azimuth steering.

pattern of a European urban area is classified as follows: during day time at weekdays, user traffic is distributed mainly at workplace while for night time, user traffic is mainly located in residential area. Similarly, during the weekends and special events, user traffic can be distributed at some distinct hot spots such as restaurant districts. Thus, to confirm the data traffic distribution in the service area, the trial and error method was used here. After implementing the antenna azimuth mounting in the cell Aspropirgos_L(272), the dynamic antenna azimuth scanning was set per 15° step within the steering range ($\pm 15^\circ$) each quarter-hour(15minutes) for a day within a predefined time scale. The dynamic azimuth scanning was repeated for a week time and the KPI files from the OSS of the Basestation were collected every quarter-hour for each steering step. After counting and evaluating, among others, the data traffic samples during the week course, as shown in Table I, the high usage area was identified by offsetting the antenna azimuth to $+15^\circ$ for the cell Aspropirgos_L (272).

TABLE I

TRAFFIC SAMPLES DURING A WEEK COURSE FOR PER 15° STEERING STEP

	-15°	0°	15°
Day 1	8108	8855	9054
Day 2	6556	6640	6984
Day 3	11045	11925	13013
Day 4	11441	12577	13539
Day 5	10770	12836	14079
Day 6	11591	13017	14192
Day 7	10841	11956	12972
Weekly	70352	77806	83833

C. Evaluation Results

The collected KPI files from the OSS of the basestation for the selected cell Aspropirgos_L (272) before and post dynamic antenna azimuth steering are compared. In order to make the collected data as accurate as possible, a full 9 week (63days) period of time before and post azimuth offsetting for the cell Aspropirgos_L (272) were analyzed respectively and the corresponding KPIs in terms of Drop Call Rate(%), Access Failure Rate(%), Voice Traffic(Erlang) and Data Traffic(Mbits) for the cell of Aspropirg before and post the dynamic antenna azimuth mounting were compared. As can be seen from Figure 7, the average voice drop call rate and access failure rate for this cell was reduced by 15% and 3.8% respectively by steering the antenna azimuth heading to (+15° heading) for a 9 week time course. The total voice traffic and data traffic in Erlangs and Mbits was increased by 13.48% and 21.67% respectively during the same period of time which means through steering the antenna azimuth to the best headings, the average mobile users' QoS was increased in this cell. Also, the KPIs were collected for the whole cluster of Thriasio Pedio for the same time period before and after the antenna azimuth implementations on multiple cells in the area of more than 100 cells, it shows that both the DCR and AFR for the whole cluster are reduced by 13% approximately and the Voice and Data Traffic is increased by 8% and 5% respectively.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has set out a concept for employing dynamic antenna azimuth planning at the basestation for any broadband mobile network to provide improved QoS and increased performance. A novel automatic antenna azimuth steering system has been designed and proposed to identify the optimum azimuth heading in the antenna horizontal plane. Real live mobile network performance results have shown that a typical data traffic can be increased by 21.67% (Cell Aspropirgos) and 5% (Thriasio Pedio) respectively when applying the dynamic antenna azimuth planning techniques proposed herein. Due to proved gains in the SNR, the performance of cell is expected to increase proportionally. As it is well known, with the expected technology evolution (5G), the more bandwidth availability, the enhanced Modulation and Coding schemes, and the MIMO and massive MIMO technology, the proposed antenna azimuth planning technique can be used to improve the current and future network performance.

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Fig. 7. a), b), c) and d) DCR%, AFR%, Erlangs and Mbits of the cell before and post dynamic azimuth planning.

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